

Do Undergraduate Medical Students Use and Value Mathematics Skills?

Hakimah Bahzad, Abdifatax Ahmed, Joseph Harbison, Cathy Cunningham.

Discipline of Medical Education, School of Medicine, Trinity College Dublin.

Prospective medical students in Ireland typically gain high marks in mathematics but medical courses have little mathematical content. We explored medical students' usage of mathematics during their studies and their views on its usefulness and whether mathematics should be a training requirement. Participants completed an anonymous 14-item online survey. 50 students who had completed the Leaving Certificate examination (LC) and 18 A-Level students responded. 62% of LC students reported completing a mathematics problem since entering medical school. 48% used mathematics at least once or twice a month and 16 reported that they found it at least moderately useful. 58% thought mathematics knowledge helped their medical studies. 60% thought mathematics should remain a requirement for medicine. There was no significant difference from the A-level group. We found that mathematics was perceived of some use to the students but it was not regarded as being of great value.

Keywords: medical education, mathematics knowledge, mathematics usage

Introduction

Undergraduate medicine courses in Irish universities are highly competitive requiring both high examination grades and the completion of an aptitude test. Bonus points in LC higher level mathematics mean medical students typically enter with high mathematics grades and competency. There is no specific mathematical element to the curriculum in medical school.

This study explored Trinity College Dublin (TCD) medical students' usage of mathematics during their course, their perceived usefulness of mathematics, and their views on whether it should be a requirement to enter medicine. We compared the responses from students in their first two pre-clinical years with those from the senior, clinical years (years three to five). We also compared responses from LC and A-Level students.

There is evidence that mathematics can help understanding, prediction, treatment and data processing within medicine. Rolison (2020) found that lower numeracy skills were linked to misinterpreting statistical health risks. Considering the use of mathematical and numeracy skills in decision making, it would seem that having a good mathematical foundation would be beneficial to medical students.

Methodology

Following ethical approval, TCD medical students were invited in March 2023 to complete a survey by email and anonymous data were collected through an online survey tool. Demographic data were collected on gender and year of study. First year students are typically aged from 17 to 19 years. The course is 5 to 6 years in duration. The survey had 14 questions trialled for potential responses during survey development. The survey included 4 Likert scales (five-to-seven-point scales), 9 closed questions and 1 open question.

Results

Complete responses were received from 80 medical students out of 970 medical students from years one to five. Of these respondents, 50 had completed the LC and 18 had completed A-levels. The remaining students had completed a range of other qualifications varying from the International Baccalaureate to undergraduate degrees. The sample was representative in terms of gender; 55% of current medical undergraduates in TCD are female.

Of the 50 LC responders, 34 were female and 16 were male. 25 were in pre-clinical years (years one and two) and 25 were in clinical years (years three, four and five). 31 (62%) of the students reported having solved a mathematics problem since entering medical school. 24 used mathematics at least once or twice a month. 16 thought mathematics was extremely or moderately useful, 18 slightly useful and 13 useless.

When asked about situations '*where you thought having a better understanding of mathematics would help in your medical studies?*', 29 (58%) responded definitely or probably yes. Thirty of the 50 thought that mathematics should remain a LC requirement for entry.

Using Chi square tests, significant differences were found between pre-clinical and clinical students about how often they used mathematics (1-2 times per month or more frequent 44% vs 56%, $X^2 = 0.7$, $p = 0.4$) or whether mathematics was useful to them (72% vs 68%, $X^2 = 0.1$, $p = 0.75$). No difference was found between students who had taken the LC or A-levels in whether they found mathematics useful 34/50 (68%) vs 11/18 (61%), $X^2 = 0.3$, $p = 0.6$. There was also no difference in whether they felt mathematics should be a requirement to enter medicine 30/50 (60%) vs 10/18 (56%), $X^2 = 0.1$ $p = 0.7$ chi square.

Discussion

Whilst few students had any great hostility towards mathematics, only about one third felt it was more than slightly useful, a single respondent thought it was extremely useful and 5 said it definitely helped their medical studies. That acknowledged, 31 reported solving a mathematics problem since medical school entry; being used in calculation of drug doses and in situations such as calculating renal function. The majority of both LC and A Level students agreed that mathematics should remain an admission requirement.

References:

Rolison, J.J. (2020) Understanding health risk comprehension: The role of math anxiety, subjective numeracy, and objective numeracy. *Medical Decision Making*, 40(2), 204-215. doi:10.1177/0272989X20904725